

USE OF NEW TECHNOLOGIES FOR DIGITAL IMAGES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN CONSTRUCTION

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Abstract: In the article, the modern urban planning environment reveals the features of the light composition as a complex art and psychological event in fine arts.

Key words: Composition, volatile spous form and light composition, mediaVall, city mutual, village houses, modern houses.

The activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan as an independent state have opened new horizons in the field of national architecture and urban planning. The new social and economic programs have changed its life. The urban environment is a third party to create a dependent of urban environment. The created of this environment is important for the townspeople to combine the relationship with the city, to have prosperous and meaningful life.

In the 1930s of the 20th century, the use of digital technologies in the design of urban environment on the use of digital technologies Corbye wrote:

"Lighting cities is one day entering the entire direction of new art, where the architecture, painter and electrical engineers will provide unprecedented

masterpieces." In the 10s of the last century, they began to use eye-catching signs in the West and for the first time decorative illumination of architectural devices increased. Lighten projections were static images in the form of signs, symbols and decorations.

Natural and artificial light is an active composite and artistic tools of the formation of the architectural image. Artificial lighting restores the dark and dark features of buildings or structures under the rays of the sun or the spread of the sky or lead to full-time lights using theater equipment and effects. The lighting can also follow certain compositional principles. One of the main methods of considering architecture as stable and solid is a solid tool for opening a building tectonics. Visually emphasizes the constructive interaction of structures and techniques developed, taking into account the role of the new building, the character of lighting, and the rhythm of light, architectures and designers to implement their ideas on the birthday. They actively use the route such as videoeps when conducting light shows. In many countries (Australia, Germany, France, Russia, etc.) are held annually by light festivals, which are distinguished by spectators and video effects. Well-known architects (J. Nuvel, B. Chumi, T. Ando, etc.), creating their projects with artists and light designers. Today, special attention is paid to the design of the coverage of all stages of the design all the stages of the design, lighting projects for all cities and individual architectural ensembles are being implemented. Change the architectural style of the building through the transfer of dynamic and static images of architects and designs using different light effects; Creating different illusions (water, live statues, building movement, etc.). There are two main directions using similar technologies - mediaarchitecture and videoeps.

The development of LETMODIOD technology has led to a relatively new area of state-artistic art - in the media surarchitecture. Plastic LED Video Facades The appearance of videos allowed cities to look at the problems and opportunities of urban lighting. Mediafood is the virtual architectural crust for static architectural forms, which uses the individual appearance of the building, to establish emotional

communication between the building, the city, and its inhabitants. This construction plays an architectural dominant role, often becomes an amazing sign that attracts tourists at the same time. In this context, housing construction and infrastructure, co-social sector, transport and communications, as well as the problems of employment of the most complex and serious social issues, as well as the most complex and serious social issues, as well as the most complex and serious social issues. It is becoming a direction that can serve as a very acceptable field of production and servicing.

Buildings built in rural areas.

The historic experience of most periods shows that the determination of the industry of development as a priority of development is a decisive tool for the restoration of the national economy. For example, during the 1930-crisis in the 1930s called Great Depression, the United States has introduced a system of loans to build individual housing construction system, and this reform has become a crucial role in the

restoration of economic growth. In time, such programs were adopted to stimulate and restore the economy in Germany, the United Kingdom, Scandinavian and other countries.

Zamanar multi-storey residential buildings built in Tashkent.

It is not now possible to consider 50 percent of the population of Uzbekistan, or about 16 million people living in ages, and the scope of complex tasks that we need to resolve in this area. It should be noted that in the ages of this area, more than 150,000 new families have been formed in the ages of 150,000 families, and during the years of independent development, more than 2,600,000 young families have emerged, and they are not needed to get home. In this regard, it is clear that it is time to reconsider the approaches, methods and practice in rural areas for many years in agriculture, and it is even more clearer that it is life that life is pushing forward.

Conclusion: Business design and construction of cities after the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan was paid to the development. In particular, the structures of

modern building, celestial buildings are being built in cities. In this case, mainly cities are being usplified by digital images of modern development. The number of population living in new housing estes, new schools, kindergartens, agricultural medical centers, trade offices and sports facilities is also being built on the basis of standard projects and is handed over to the population.

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